

On Pathos Lict Subdivision of a Tree

Keerthi G.Mirajkar and Iramma M.Kadakol

(Department of Mathematics, Karnatak Arts College, Dharwad-580 001, Karnataka, India)

Email: keerthi_gm@yahoo.co.in, iramma.k@gmail.com

Abstract: Let G be a graph and $E_1 \subset E(G)$. A Smarandachely E_1 -lict graph $n^{E_1}(G)$ of a graph G is the graph whose point set is the union of the set of lines in E_1 and the set of cutpoints of G in which two points are adjacent if and only if the corresponding lines of G are adjacent or the corresponding members of G are incident. Here the lines and cutpoints of G are member of G . Particularly, if $E_1 = E(G)$, a Smarandachely $E(G)$ -lict graph $n^{E(G)}(G)$ is abbreviated to *lict graph of G* and denoted by $n(G)$. In this paper, the concept of pathos lict sub-division graph $P_n[S(T)]$ is introduced. Its study is concentrated only on trees. We present a characterization of those graphs, whose lict sub-division graph is planar, outerplanar, maximal outerplanar and minimally nonouterplanar. Further, we also establish the characterization for $P_n[S(T)]$ to be eulerian and hamiltonian.

Key Words: pathos, path number, Smarandachely lict graph, lict graph, pathos lict sub-division graphs, Smarandache path k -cover, pathos point.

AMS(2010): 05C10, 05C99

§1. Introduction

The concept of *pathos* of a graph G was introduced by Harary [1] as a collection of minimum number of line disjoint open paths whose union is G . The path number of a graph G is the number of paths in a pathos. Stanton [7] and Harary [3] have calculated the path number for certain classes of graphs like trees and complete graphs. The *subdivision of a graph G* is obtained by inserting a point of degree 2 in each line of G and is denoted by $S(G)$. The path number of a subdivision of a tree $S(T)$ is equal to K , where $2K$ is the number of odd degree point of $S(T)$. Also, the end points of each path of any pathos of $S(T)$ are odd points. The *lict graph $n(G)$* of a graph G is the graph whose point set is the union of the set of lines and the set of cutpoints of G in which two points are adjacent if and only if the corresponding lines of G are adjacent or the corresponding members of G are incident. Here the lines and cutpoints of G are member of G .

For any integer $k \geq 1$, a Smarandache path k -cover of a graph G is a collection ψ of paths in G such that each edge of G is in at least one path of ψ and two paths of ψ have at most

¹Received July 18, 2010. Accepted December 25, 2010.

k vertices in common. Thus if $k = 1$ and every edge of G is in exactly one path in ψ , then a Smarandache path k -cover of G is a simple path cover of G . See [8].

By a graph we mean a finite, undirected graph without loops or multiple lines. We refer to the terminology of [1]. The *pathos lict subdivision of a tree T* is denoted as $P_n[S(T)]$ and is defined as the graph, whose point set is the union of set of lines, set of paths of pathos and set of cutpoints of $S(T)$ in which two points are adjacent if and only if the corresponding lines of $S(T)$ are adjacent and the line lies on the corresponding path P_i of pathos and the lines are incident to the cutpoints. Since the system of path of pathos for a $S(T)$ is not unique, the corresponding pathos lict subdivision graph is also not unique. The pathos lict subdivision graph is defined for a tree having at least one cutpoint.

In Figure 1, a tree T and its subdivision graph $S(T)$, and their pathos lict subdivision graphs $P_n[S(T)]$ are shown.

Figure 1

The *line degree* of a line uv in $S(T)$ is the sum of the degrees of u and v . The pathos length is the number of lines which lies on a particular path P_i of pathos of $S(T)$. A pendant pathos is a path P_i of pathos having unit length which corresponds to a pendant line in $S(T)$. A pathos point is a point in $P_n[S(T)]$ corresponding to a path of pathos of $S(T)$. If G is planar graph, the *innerpoint number* $i(G)$ of a graph G is the minimum number of vertices not belonging to the boundary of the exterior region in any embedding of the plane. A graph is said to be minimally nonouterplanar if $i(G) = 1$ was given by [4].

We need the following for immediate use.

Remark 1.1 For any tree T , $n[S(T)]$ is a subgraph of $P_n[S(T)]$.

Remark 1.2 For any tree T , $T \subseteq S(T)$.

Remark 1.3 If the line degree of a nonpendant line in $S(T)$ is odd(even), the corresponding point in $P_n[S(T)]$ is of even(odd) degree.

Remark 1.4 The pendant line in $S(T)$ is always odd degree and the corresponding point in $P_n[S(T)]$ is of odd degree.

Remark 1.5 For any tree T with C cutpoints, the number of cutpoints in $n[S(T)]$ is equal to sum of the lines incident to C in T .

Remark 1.6 For any tree T , the number of blocks in $n[S(T)]$ is equal to the sum of the cutpoints and lines of T .

Remark 1.7 $n[S(T)]$ is connected if and only if T is connected.

Theorem 1.1([5]) If G is a non trivial connected (p, q) graph whose points have degree d_i and l_i be the number of lines to which cutpoint C_i belongs in G , then lict graph $n(G)$ has $q + \sum C_i$ points and $-q + \sum[\frac{d_i^2}{2} + l_i]$ lines.

Theorem 1.2([5]) The lict graph $n(G)$ of a graph G is planar if and only if G is planar and the degree of each point is atmost 3.

Theorem 1.3([2]) Every maximal outerplanar graph G with p points has $2p - 3$ lines.

Theorem 1.4([6]) A graph is a nonempty path if and only if it is a connected graph with $p \geq 2$ points and $\sum d_i^2 - 4p + 6 = 0$.

Theorem 1.5([2]) A graph G is eulerian if and only if every point of G is of even degree.

§2. Pathos Lict Subdivision Graph

In the following Theorem we obtain the number of points and lines of $P_n[S(T)]$.

Theorem 2.1 For any (p, q) graph T , whose points have degree d_i and cutpoints C have degree C_j , then the pathos lict sub-division graph $P_n[S(T)]$ has $(3q + C + P_i)$ points and $\frac{1}{2} \sum d_i^2 + 4q + \sum C_j$ lines.

Proof By Theorem 1.1, $n(T)$ has $q + \sum c$ points by subdivision of T $n(S(T))$ contains $2q + q + \sum c$ points and by Remark 1.1, $P_nS(T)$ will contain $3q + \sum c + P_i$ points, where P_i is the path number. By the definition of $n(T)$, it follows that $L(T)$ is a subgraph of $n(T)$. Also, subgraphs of $L(T)$ are line-disjoint subgraphs of $n[S(T)]$ whose union is $L(T)$ and the cutpoints c of T having degree C_j are also the members of $n[s(T)]$. Hence this implies that $n[s(T)]$ contains $-q + \frac{1}{2} \sum d_i^2 + \sum c_j$ lines. Apart from these lines every subdivision of T generates

a line and a cutpoint c of degree 2. This creates $q + 2q$ lines in $n[S(T)]$. Thus $n[S(T)]$ has $\frac{1}{2} \sum d_i^2 + \sum c_j + 2q$ lines. Further, the pathos contribute $2q$ lines to $P_n[S(T)]$. Hence $P_n[S(T)]$ contains $\frac{1}{2} \sum d_i^2 + \sum c_j + 4q$ lines. \square

Corollary 2.1 *For any (p, q) graph T , the number of regions in $P_n[S(T)]$ is $2(p + q) - 3$.*

§3. Planar Pathos Lict Sub-division Graph

In this section we obtain the condition for planarity of pathos.

Theorem 3.1 *$P_n[S(T)]$ of a tree T is planar if and only if $\Delta(T) \leq 3$.*

Proof Suppose $P_n[S(T)]$ is planar. Assume $\Delta(T) \leq 4$. Let v be a point of degree 4 in T . By Remark 1.1, $n[S(T)]$ is a subgraph of $P_n[S(T)]$ and by Theorem 1.2, $P_n[S(T)]$ is non-planar. Clearly, $P_n[S(T)]$ is non-planar, a contradiction.

Conversely, suppose $\Delta(T) \leq 3$. By Theorem 1.2, $n[S(T)]$ is planar. Further each block of $n[S(T)]$ is either K_3 or K_4 . The pathos point is adjacent to atmost two vertices of each block of $n[S(T)]$. This gives a planar $P_n[S(T)]$. \square

We next give a characterization of trees whose pathos lict subdivision of trees are outerplanar and maximal outerplanar.

Theorem 3.2 *The pathos lict sub-division graph $P_n[S(T)]$ of a tree T is outerplanar if and only if $\Delta(T) \leq 2$.*

Proof Suppose $P_n[S(T)]$ is outerplanar. Assume T has a point v of degree 3. The lines incident to v and the cut-point v form $\langle K_4 \rangle$ as a subgraph in $n[S(T)]$. Hence $P_n[S(T)]$ is non-outerplanar, a contradiction.

Conversely, suppose T is a path P_m of length $m \geq 1$, by definition each block of $n[S(T)]$ is K_3 and $n[S(T)]$ has $2m - 1$ blocks. Also, $S(T)$ has exactly one path of pathos and the pathos point is adjacent to atmost two points of each block of $n[S(T)]$. The pathos point together with each block form $2m - 1$ number of $\langle K_4 - x \rangle$ subgraphs in $P_n[S(T)]$. Hence $P_n[S(T)]$ is outerplanar. \square

Theorem 3.3 *The pathos lict sub-division graph $P_n[S(T)]$ of a tree T is maximal outerplanar if and only if.*

Proof Suppose $P_n[S(T)]$ is maximal outerplanar. Then $P_n[S(T)]$ is connected. Hence by Remark 1.7, T is connected. Suppose $P_n[S(T)]$ is $K_4 - x$, then clearly, T is K_2 . Let T be any connected tree with $p > 2$ points, q lines and having path number k and C cut-points. Then clearly, $P_n[S(T)]$ has $3q + k + C$ points and $\frac{1}{2} \sum d_i^2 + 4q + \sum C_j$ lines. Since $P_n[S(T)]$ is maximal

outerplanar, by Theorem 1.3, it has $[2(3q + k + C) - 3]$ lines. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \sum d_i^2 + 4q + \sum C_j &= [2(3q + k + C) - 3] \\ &= [2(3(p - 1) + k + C) - 3] \\ &= 6p - 6 + 2k + 2C - 3 \\ &= 6p + 2k + 2C - 9. \end{aligned}$$

But for $k = 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum d_i^2 + 8q + 2 \sum C_j &= 12p + 4C - 18 + 4, \\ \sum d_i^2 + 2 \sum C_j &= 4p + 4C - 6, \\ \sum d_i^2 + 2 \sum C_j - 4p - 4C + 6 &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Since every cut-point is of degree two in a path, we have,

$$\sum C_j = 2C.$$

Therefore

$$\sum d_i^2 + 6 - 4p = 4C - 2 \times 2C = 0.$$

Hence $\sum d_i^2 + 6 - 4p = 0$. By Theorem 1.4, it follows that T is a non-empty path.

Conversely, Suppose T is a non-empty path. We now prove that $P_n[S(T)]$ is maximal outerplanar by induction on the number of points (≥ 2). Suppose T is K_2 . Then $P_n[S(T)] = K_4 - x$. Hence it is maximal outerplanar. As the inductive hypothesis, let the pathos list subdivision of a non-empty path P with n points be maximal outerplanar. We now show that $P_n[S(T)]$ of a path P with $n + 1$ points is maximal outerplanar. First we prove that it is outerplanar. Let the point and line sequence of the path P' be $v_1, e_1, v_2, e_2, v_3, e_3, \dots, v_n, e_n, v_{n+1}$. P' , $S(P')$ and $P_n[S(P')]$ are shown in Figure 2. Without loss of generality, $P' - v_{n+1} = P$. By inductive hypothesis $P_n[S(P)]$ is maximal outerplanar. Now the point v_{n+1} is one point more in $P_n[S(P')]$ than in $P_n[S(P)]$. Also there are only eight lines (e'_{n-1}, e_n) , (e'_{n-1}, e_{n-1}) , (e_{n-1}, e_n) , (e_n, R) , (e_n, e'_n) , (e_n, C'_n) , (C'_n, e'_n) , (e'_n, R) more in $P_n[S(P')]$. Clearly, the induced subgraph on the points $e'_{n-1}, C_{n-1}, e_n, e'_n, C'_n, R$ is not K_4 . Hence $P_n[S(P')]$ is outerplanar. We now prove $P_n[S(P')]$ is maximal outerplanar. Since $P_n[S(P)]$ is maximal outerplanar, it has $2(3q + C + 1) - 3$ lines. The outerplanar graph $P_n[S(P')]$ has $2(3q + C + 1) - 3 + 8$ lines $= 2[3(q + 1) + (C + 1) + 1] - 3$ lines. By Theorem 1.3, $P_n[S(P')]$ is maximal outerplanar. \square

Theorem 3.4 *For any tree T , $P_n[S(T)]$ is minimally nonouterplanar if and only if $\Delta(T) \leq 3$ and T has a unique point of degree 3.*

Proof Suppose $P_n[S(T)]$ is minimally non-outerplanar. Assume $\Delta(T) > 3$. By Theorem 3.1, $P_n[S(T)]$ is nonplanar, a contradiction. Hence $\Delta(T) \leq 3$.

Assume $\Delta(T) < 3$. By Theorem 3.2, $P_n[S(T)]$ is outerplanar, a contradiction. Thus $\Delta(T) = 3$.

Assume there exist two points of degree 3 in T . Then $n[S(T)]$ has at least two blocks as K_4 . Any pathos point of $S(T)$ is adjacent to atmost two points of each block in $n[S(T)]$ which gives $i(P_n[S(T)]) > 1$, a contradiction. Hence T has exactly one point point of degree 3.

Conversely, suppose every point of T has degree ≤ 3 and has a unique point of degree 3, then $n[S(T)]$ has exactly one block as K_4 and remaining blocks are K_3 's. Each pathos point is adjacent to atmost two points of each block. Hence $i(P_n[S(T)]) = 1$. \square

Figure 2

§4. Traversability in Pathos Lict Subdivision of a Tree

In this section, we characterize the trees whose $P_n[S(T)]$ is eulerian and hamiltonian.

Theorem 4.1 *For any non-trivial tree T , the pathos lict subdivision of a tree is non-eulerian.*

Proof Let T be a non-trivial tree. Remark 1.4 implies $P_n[S(T)]$ always contains a point of odd degree. Hence by Theorem 1.5, the result follows. \square

Theorem 4.2 *The pathos lict subdivision $P_n[S(T)]$ of a tree T is hamiltonian if and only if every cut-point of T is even of degree.*

Proof If $T = P_2$, then $P_n[S(T)]$ is $K_4 - x$. If T is a tree with $p \geq 3$ points. Suppose $P_n[S(T)]$ is hamiltonian. Assume that T has at least one cut-point v of odd degree m . Then $G = K_{1,m}$ is a subgraph of T . Clearly, $n(S(K_{1,m})) = K_{m+1}$, together with each point of K_m incident to a line of K_3 . In number of path of pathos of $S(T)$ there exist at least one path of pathos P_i such that it begins with the cut-point v of $S(T)$. In $P_n[S(T)]$ each pathos point is adjacent to exactly two points of K_m . Further the pathos beginning with the cut-point v of $S(T)$ is adjacent to exactly one point of K_m in $n(S(T))$. Hence this creates a cut-point in $P_n[S(T)]$, a contradiction.

Conversely, suppose every cut-point of T is even. Then every path of pathos starts and ends at pendant points of T .

We consider the following cases.

Case 1 If T has only cut-points of degree two. Clearly, T is a path. Further $S(T)$ is also a path with $p + q$ points and has exactly one path of pathos. Let $T = P_l, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_l$ is a path. Now $S(T): v_1, v'_1, v_2, v'_2, \dots, v'_{l-1}, v_l$ for all $v_i \in V[S(P_l)]$ such that $v_i v'_i = e_i, v'_i v_{i+1} = e'_i$ are consecutive lines and for all $e_i, e'_i \in E[S(P_n)]$. Further $V[n(S(T))] = \{e_1, e'_1, e_2, e'_2, \dots, e_i, e'_i\} \cup \{C'_1, C_1, C'_2, C_2, \dots, C'_i\}$ where, $(C'_1, C_1, C'_2, C_2, \dots, C'_i)$ are cut-points of $S(T)$. Since each block is a triangle in $n(S(T))$ and each block consist of points as $B_1 = (e_1 C'_1 e'_1), B_2 = (e_2 C'_2 e'_2), \dots, B_m = (e_i C'_i e'_i)$. In $P_n[S(T)]$, the pathos point w is adjacent to $e_1, e'_1, e_2, e'_2, \dots, e_i, e'_i$. Hence, $P_n[S(T)] = e_1, e'_1, e_2, e'_2, \dots, e_i, e'_i \cup (C'_1, C_1, C'_2, C_2, \dots, C'_i) \cup w$ form a cycle as $w e_1 C'_1 e'_1 C_1 e_2 C'_2 e'_2 \dots e'_i w$ containing all the points of $P_n[S(T)]$. Hence $P_n[S(T)]$ is hamiltonian.

Case 2 If T has all cut-points of even degree and is not a path.

we consider the following subcases of this case.

Subcase 2.1. If T has exactly one cut-point v of even degree m , $v = \Delta(T)$ and is $K_{1,m}$. Clearly, $S(K_{1,m}) = F$, such that $E(F) = \{e_1, e'_1, e_2, e'_2, \dots, e_q, e'_q\}$. Now $n(F)$ contains point set as $\{e_1, e'_1, e_2, e'_2, \dots, e_q, e'_q\} \cup \{v, C'_1, C'_2, C'_3, \dots, C'_q\}$. For $S[K_{1,m}]$, it has $\frac{m}{2}$ paths of pathos with pathos point as $P_1, P_2, \dots, P_{\frac{m}{2}}$. By definition of $P_n[S(T)]$, each pathos point is adjacent to exactly two points of $n(S(T))$. Also, $V[P_n[S(T)]] = \{e_1, e'_1, e_2, e'_2, \dots, e_q, e'_q\} \cup \{v, C'_1, C'_2, C'_3, \dots, C'_q\} \cup \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_{\frac{m}{2}}\}$. Then there exist a cycle containing all the points of $P_n[S(T)]$ as $P_1, e'_1, C'_1, e_1, v, e_2, C'_2, e'_2, P_2, \dots, P_{\frac{m}{2}}, e'_{q-1}, C'_{q-1}, e_{q-1}, e_q, C'_q, e'_q, P_1$.

Subcase 2.2. Assume T has more than one cut-point of even degree. Then in $n(S(T))$ each block is complete and every cut-point lies on exactly two blocks of $n(S(T))$. Let $V[n(S(T))] = \{e_1, e'_1, e_2, e'_2, \dots, e_q, e'_q\} \cup \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_i\} \cup \{C'_1, C'_2, C'_3, \dots, C'_q\} \cup \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_j\}$. But each P_j is adjacent to exactly two point of the block B_j except $\{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_i\} \cup \{C'_1, C'_2, C'_3, \dots, C'_q\}$ and all these points together form a hamiltonian cycle of the type, $\{P_1, e'_1, C'_1, e_1, v, e_2, C'_2, e'_2, P_2, \dots, P_r, e'_k, C'_k, e_k, e_{k+1}, C'_{k+1}, e'_{k+1}, P_{r+1}, \dots, P_j, e'_{q-1}, C'_{q-1}, e_{q-1}, e_q, C'_q, e'_q, P_1\}$.

Hence $P_n[S(T)]$ is hamiltonian. \square

References

- [1] Harary. F, *Annals of New York, Academy of Sciences*, (1974)175.

- [2] Harary. F, *Graph Theory*, Addison-Wesley, Reading, Mass,1969.
- [3] Harary F and Schwenik A.J, *Graph Theory and Computing*, Ed.Read R.C, Academic press, New York,(1972).
- [4] Kulli V.R, *Proceedings of the Indian National Science Academy*, 61(A),(1975), 275.
- [5] Kulli V.R and Muddebihal M.H, *J. of Analysis and computation*,Vol 2, No.1(2006), 33.
- [6] Kulli V.R, *The Maths Education*, (1975),9.
- [7] Stanton R.G, Cowan D.D and James L.O, *Proceedings of the louisiana conference on combinatorics*, *Graph Theory and Computation* (1970), 112.
- [8] S. Arumugam and I. Sahul Hamid, *International J.Math.Combin.* Vol.3,(2008), 94-104.